

MEDIA LITERACY AS A DETERMINANT OF EFFECTIVE PUBLIC HEALTH COMMUNICATION IN THE DIGITAL AGE

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Abstract

Recently, media literacy has emerged as a critical factor that has the ability to influence individual's perspective. It also influence the way how individual interpret and respond to public health messages. This study investigates media literacy as a determinant of effective public health communication in the digital age, focusing on the general public of Bahawalpur, Pakistan. For this study researcher adopted quantitative, cross-sectional survey design and data were collected from 420 respondents using a structured questionnaire. A five ppoint likert-scale was used to measure media literacy, message comprehension, trust in health information, and behavioral response through the questionnaire. Furthermore, data were analyzed using SPSS, applying descriptive statistics, correlation analysis, and multiple regression techniques. The findings reveal a strong and statistically significant positive relationship between media literacy and public health communication effectiveness. Media literacy emerged as the most influential interpreter of effective public health communication. Moreover, the findings of the study revealed that education level of participants of the study significantly influenced media literacy. However, gender differences were not found statistically significant. The study concludes that enhancing media literacy is essential for improving public understanding and compliance with public health communication in digital environments. There is dire need to make media literacy a part of curriculum in mainstream education system.

INTRODUCTION

Life style of human beings is uprising due to the modernization of digital platform. It transformed every part of life and the way public get information though digital technologies. Public health information reached the public through diverse digital platforms including YouTube, Facebook etc. Therefore, recently, health experts increasingly rely on digital platforms to

communicate with the public. Digital media provide such platform that assist health experts to circulate precarious information related to disease prevention, vaccination, and emergency responses for the wellbeing of human beings (Rice, 2019). On one side digital media is a great source to present information to the public, on the flip side the digital environment has enabled the rapid

spread of misinformation and disinformation. This not only undermining trust in health institutions but also complicating public health efforts and rises question in the public about the authenticity of the information. Diverse scholars define media literacy as the ability to access, analyze, and evaluate media content presented to them. Thus, media literacy enable individuals to navigate the complex landscape of the information available online (Mahmudah, 2025).

Health literacy is essential to the well-being of individual and it is consistently linked to ensure effective public communication for healthier behaviors in digital environment. One of its prerequisite, it is beneficial for a prosperous and productive society. The benefits of having the health literacy is that population productive increases as they follow health care routine and results in intensification of economic growth and sustainable economic development. However, the increasing volume of health misinformation during events like pandemics highlights a gap in media literacy that can undermine public health goals (Morley, 2020). This researcher study was designed to examine the connection between media literacy and public health communication. It also study the effectiveness of media literacy for health communication, identifying theoretical foundations and implications of the study for policy and practice.

1.1 Statement of the Problem

The rapid expansion of digital media has transformed the way to teach public related to health communication. It is because media literacy enabled the public to understand what is presented to them through media about health. Furthermore, health authorities, organizations, and professionals to broadcast information widely through digital platforms to educate general public about the changing environment in health sector (Arias, et, al, 2023). In recent years digital shift has

increased access to health-related information. Moreover, it was also found that it has simultaneously intensified the circulation of misinformation, disinformation, and unverified health content. In such an environment, individuals are frequently exposed to contradictory and misleading messages regarding disease prevention, treatment, and health policies, which can undermine public trust. It is also observed that negatively influence health-related decision-making (Mutlu, 2025). Despite the growing dependence on digital platforms for public health messaging, there is limited empirical understanding of the role media literacy. Individuals' ability to critically evaluate and respond to these messages is shaped by the media literacy. Many public health communication strategies assume that access to information alone is sufficient to produce informed and compliant health behavior. However, evidence suggests that individuals with less exposure without critical interpretive skills may increase confusion. Therefore, these people have more vulnerability towards the misinformation and there is dire need to develop resistance to evidence-based health guidance.

Furthermore, existing research often treats media literacy as a secondary or peripheral variable without understanding long-term diseases often affect the productivity of people. Therefore, there is dire need to examining media literacy as a central determinant of communication effectiveness so that individual's likelihood increased. Media literacy is required for successful employment and work (Parandeh, 2022). There is also a lack of integrated studies that systematically assess how media literacy influences comprehension, trust, and behavioral responses to public health communication in digital contexts. This research study is deigned to fill the gap that media exposure shape health communication outcomes differently. In digitally diverse societies

where variations in education, digital competence prevailed this problem is addressed in this study. Researcher found that insufficient empirical research studies were conducted in the field of media literacy as a determining factor. Moreover, in this digital age effectiveness of public health communication cannot be studied without a clear understanding of its relationship with public health improvement and its effectiveness for risk remaining and counterproductive in addressing misinformation and promoting positive health behaviors.

1.2 Research Objectives

- To measure media literacy levels among digital information consumers.
- To assess the effectiveness of public health communication strategies in relation to media literacy.
- To identify demographic patterns influencing media literacy and health outcomes.
- To suggest policy recommendations for enhancing health communication through media literacy education.

1.3 Significance of the Study

This study holds theoretical, practical, and policy-oriented significance in the field of research through this study, researcher studied media literacy as a factor of effective public health communication in this digital age. Talking about the theoretical significance of this study, it was found that it was lied in its contribution to the academic literature because this study integrated media literacy within established frameworks of public health communication. It added more in the existing literature by providing theoretical understanding of media literacy. It stated that media literacy is not merely as an individual skill but a mediating factor that shapes message interpretation by the public, trust formation of the individual towards the message presented to them,

and behavioral outcomes. However, from a practical perspective, the findings of the study provided a valuable insights for public health professionals, media practitioners, and communication strategists. So that they can further understand how varying levels of media literacy affect public response to health messages. Researcher adopted such research design that assist the researcher to study the impact of media literacy and presents reliable and audience-sensitive communication strategies.

2. Literature Review

2.1 Conceptual Foundations

The digital age has transformed not only the *channels* through which health information is disseminated, but also the *skills* required to interpret, evaluate, and act upon that information. These competencies are foundational for navigating the vast and often conflicting landscape of digital health information. Media literacy intersects with health literacy because it is the ability to obtain, process, and understand basic health information available online or on digital platforms. Therefore, public appropriate for decision-making after getting health literacy. In the digital context, this intersection has often been operationalized as digital health literacy (DHL), which includes critical thinking skills along with technical navigation abilities.

2.2 Media Literacy and Public Health Outcomes

Digital media have democratized the production and consumption of information. Digital media is considered as a powerful tool for public health communication (Okhwarobo, 2024). Health communication has contributed much towards the health of public and assist in adopting health care behaviours. Recently, this field is gaining acknowledgement among public because of its emphasis on adopting changing human behavior. Digital media platforms such as Facebook,

Twitter, YouTube, and WhatsApp allow public to circulate information instantly. Information reached to the wide audience during health crises can be fruitful for those who critically evaluate the information and misleading for the general public or those with low level of literacy. These digital platforms serve as essential channels for governments and health experts to communicate with the public. Health organizations utilize the digital platforms to communicate with a large number of the audience and updates them related to outbreaks, vaccine availability, and health guidelines (Hu, 2015).

a) Infodemic Management

Infodemic management means the systematic use of risk analysis and adopting such approaches that reduces the impact on health behavior during health emergencies. The COVID-19 pandemic highlighted how information overload lead to destabilize by the public health. Similarly, spread of misinformation can undermine efforts for improving public health. In this context public health response cannot be undermined. Systematic evidence shows that individuals with higher levels of media literacy are better able to manage health-related “infodemics”. An infodemic empower people to distinguish between credible sources and non-credible sources.

b) Digital Health Literacy and Decision-Making

Previous research studies conducted in relevant field indicate that people with media literacy are able to seek relevant health information. It enable individuals to overcome confusion and enlightening their risk-taking behaviors that assist them in making informed health decisions. For instance, research among university students in Pakistan highlighted some negative outcomes when individuals were left unchecked while using media.

c) Expanded Role of Digital Platforms

Research highlights that digital communication tools (mobile apps, telehealth, online educational platforms) can enhance health literacy. It is also observed that those who posses media literacy are able to use these communication tools for strengthening public health communication. These tools facilitate the individuals to education others, self-management, and broader engagement with health services. Only the avalibility of the tools is not required but *critical appraisal skills* are also require to ensure users can differentiate between imposing and non-authoritative content.

2.3 Media Literacy Shapes Public Health Communication

Media literacy is mandatory for the public to locate the relevant health information from diverse digital platforms including websites and social media apps. Therefore, media literacy proved to be productive for assessing information available online. It has effect on individuals through several mechanisms and navigation towards digital information. Critical evaluation skills is considered as a core component of media literacy because it enable the individuals to contextualize the search results with previously gained health information. It allows individuals to judge the credibility of sources and identify bias hidden in the content presented to them so that they were not become prey to commercial interests. Thus it is required to mitigate the influence of misrepresentation. Individuals with deficiencies in these skills lead to poorer health outcomes and misrepresentation susceptibility.

Media users with lack of critical competency often undermine the public health message and contribute to misinformation cycles. On the flip side, critical competency is required for the content creators as well because they are active media participants, such as posting or sharing health-related content. Talking about behavioral

impact, it was found that there is evidence that media and digital literacy influence health behavior adoption. Studies reviewed in media health literacy frameworks show that well-informed users demonstrate higher acceptance of preventive behaviors and are more likely to follow official health guidance during.

2.4 Contextual and Demographic Variations

While talking about the demographic variants and their impact on the media literacy, previously conducted research studies highlighted that the impact of media literacy on public health communication is mediated by sociocultural and demographic factors. It is observed that age is considered as a major factor that affect digital familiarity. Moreover, education level also has its impact on digital familiarity. As education is one of the greatest challenge in adapting to digital health environments. There is dire need for tailored media literacy interventions across age groups and education levels.

2.5 The Concept of Media Literacy

Media literacy encompasses skills necessary to critically assess media content. Media literacy provides a framework that is needed for living in the 21st century and utilizing digital information for the betterment of the society. Moreover, individuals with media literacy required evaluating sources, recognizing bias, understanding persuasive intent, and identifying misinformation (Jolls, 2014). Facebook and YouTube have been widely used to impact health performances of users, whereas Twitter and Instagram are often used to set new trends for changing behaviour. Scholars argue that digital literacy enables individuals to navigate the complexity of digital information environments, thereby influencing how health messages are interpreted and acted upon (Polanco-Levicán, 2022).

2.6 Media Literacy and Health Outcomes

Experimental research conducted to study the influence of media literacy and its impact on health suggests that individuals with higher media literacy are better equipped to discern credible health information and are less likely to be influenced by false content (Gordon, 2025). Digital health literacy enables individuals to access information present online, they can further utilize this information for the improvement of their health. Moreover, utilizing digital platforms enable individuals to navigate health information. Media literacy competency enable people to interpret health information whether the information is accurate or not. This also empower them to maintain and improve their health and people around them. These individuals tend to verify sources before accepting health information along with recognize misinformation tactics so that public can seek information from authoritative institutions and make informed health decisions for their betterment (Hung, 2014).

To sum up the whole discussion it is stated that media literacy enable individuals to navigate complex digital landscapes media literacy enhances not only individual health outcomes but also collective resilience against misinformation and health crises. Similarly, critically assess information quality, and engage responsibly with health content is supportive in enhancing media literacy particularly within vulnerable and digitally underserved populations. Furthermore, media literacy is therefore essential for strengthening public health communication strategies in contemporary digital ecosystems.

Research Questions

1. How does media literacy influence understanding and acceptance of public health messages online?

2. What is the relationship between media literacy and adherence to public health guidance?

3. How do demographic factors (age, education, digital experience) moderate this relationship?

3. Theoretical Framework

This study draws on two main theories:

3.1 Uses and Gratifications Theory

For the present study researcher adopted uses and gratification theory. This theory posits that users actively seek media content to satisfy their specific needs, for instance some uses media to collect information, some for reassurance and some for entertainment. This theory also states that people are dependent on media sources to fulfil their needs (Whiting, 2013). Individuals with higher media literacy are more selective in the information they engage with because this theory states that the media consumers are not passive rather they are active participants. Researcher adopted this study because of its relevance in the media literacy because the digital content consumers are active and they scrutinize the sources they trust before they consume.

3.2 Cognitive Processing Theory

This framework suggests that individuals interpret media messages through cognitive filters shaped by knowledge, beliefs, and skills (Ewoldsen, 2022). Researcher adopted this theory for the present study because of the relevance of this theory in the field of media because it suggest that there is similarity between human mind and computer. Both are processing and encoding data when they experience any stimuli and understand the information and response accordingly. This theory also explains that when a person experiences stimuli, their minds will look toward prior schema to help them understand this information thus when health content was presented to them they

analyze the content before consuming. Therefore, higher media literacy supports more complex and critical processing of health messages, reducing vulnerability to misinformation.

4.1 Research Design

Researcher adopted a quantitative research design while conducting the study, using a cross-sectional investigation method to observe media literacy as a determinant of effective public health communication in the digital age. The quantitative approach was selected by the researcher to measure relationships between variables objectively and to allow for statistical generalization of findings to the target population.

4.2 Population

The population of present study comprised the general public of Bahawalpur District, Pakistan. The population included male and female residents aged 18 years and above. Researcher ensured that population should have regularly access digital media platforms included social media, online news portals, and messaging applications for information consumption.

4.3 Sample Size

For the selection of sample size, researcher determined it by using Cochran's (1977) formula for large populations to ensure statistical representativeness and reliability (Kotrlík, 2001). By adopting Cochran's formula 384 participants were required for the present study but researcher included 5% more participants as a margin of error. To compensate for non-response and incomplete questionnaires, the sample size was increased to 420 respondents, ensuring adequate data for meaningful statistical analysis.

4.3.1 Sampling Technique

A multistage sampling technique was employed for sample selection at stage one area selection was

made by the researcher. Bahawalpur District was divided into urban and semi-urban localities whereas researcher selected members from urban area. Stage Two dealt with participant selection within selected localities, 420 respondents were chosen using systematic random sampling. At third stage researcher done eligibility screening and at this level only individuals aged 18 years or above with regular exposure to digital media were included. By using multiple stage of sampling researcher ensured population diversity and minimized selection bias.

4.4 Research Instruments

Data were collected using a structured questionnaire as a research instrument. Researcher adopted a self-administered questionnaire designed specifically for this study and divided into four major sections:

Section A: Demographic Information

The first section of the questionnaire based on the section used for collection of background information including age, gender, education level, occupation, and frequency of digital media use.

Section B: Media Literacy

For this part of the questionnaire, researcher used 5-point Likert scale ranging from Strongly Disagree (1) to Strongly Agree (5) to gather the viewpoint of the audience. In this section media literacy was measured using an adapted version of a Media Literacy Scale, focusing on:

- Ability to identify credible health information
- Evaluation of online sources
- Recognition of misinformation
- Critical interpretation of digital content

Section C: Public Health Communication Effectiveness

In this section, researcher adopted a 5-point Likert scale for consistency and reliability in order to assess the effectiveness of public health communication through three dimensions:

- Message comprehension
- Trust in health information
- Perceived usefulness of public health messages

Section D: Behavioral Response

In order to measured behaviour response, researcher included items related to self-reported behavioral outcomes and researcher here used 5 point likert scale for:

- Willingness to follow public health guidelines
- Information-sharing behavior
- Preventive health practices

4.5 Validity and Reliability of the Instrument

In order to ensure content validity of the questionnaire, researcher reviewed this questionnaire by experts in media studies and public health communication. Further to ensure the validity and reliability of the research tool researcher ensure to conduct a pilot study with 40 respondents from the same population but the final sample was excluded to assess clarity and consistency. Reliability was tested using Cronbach's Alpha, with values above 0.70 considered acceptable for all scales.

4.6 Data Collection Procedure

Data were collected through survey questionnaire over a period of four weeks. Respondents were informed about the purpose of the study by the researcher, and participation was voluntary. Ethical considerations such as anonymity and confidentiality were strictly observed.

4.7 Data Analysis Techniques

Data were analyzed using Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) version 26. Researcher applied statistical techniques including descriptive statistics frequencies, percentages, means, and standard deviations. These statistics were used to summarize demographic variables and scale responses. Whereas on order to ensure the reliability of the tool researcher used Cronbach's Alpha that was calculated to assess internal consistency of the research instruments. Pearson's correlation coefficient was used to examine the relationship between media literacy and public health communication effectiveness. Similarly,

multiple regression analysis was conducted to determine the predictive role of media literacy on public health communication outcomes while controlling for demographic variables. T-tests and ANOVA were used to examine differences in media literacy and communication effectiveness across demographic groups such as gender, education, and age.

4.8 Ethical Considerations

Informed consent was obtained from all participants. The study ensured confidentiality of responses and compliance with ethical standards for social science research.

5.1 Data analysis and its interpretation

Variable	Category	Frequency (f)	Percentage (%)
Gender	Male	210	50.0
	Female	210	50.0
Age	18–25 years	118	28.1
	26–35 years	142	33.8
	36–45 years	96	22.9
	46 years and above	64	15.2
Education	Intermediate or below	104	24.8
	Bachelor's degree	176	41.9
	Master's degree and above	140	33.3
Digital Media Use	Daily	298	71.0
	Occasionally	122	29.0

Table 1 presents the demographic profile of the respondents. The above mention tables presents the data related to the sample of this study which consisted of an equal representation of male and female participants (50% each), ensuring gender balance. The majority of respondents belonged to the 26–35 age group (33.8%), followed by those aged 18–25 years (28.1%), the statistics ensured that participants of the study belong to the young groups who are active users of digital apps. In

terms of education, most respondents held a bachelor's degree (41.9%) or higher (33.3%) that suggest the participants of the study has adequate educational exposure which enable them to engage with digital media content. Furthermore, a substantial proportion of respondents (71%) reported daily use of digital media, highlighting the relevance of digital platforms for public health communication in Bahawalpur.

Variable	Mean (M)	Standard Deviation (SD)
Media Literacy	3.84	0.61
Message Comprehension	3.79	0.65
Trust in Health Information	3.68	0.70
Behavioral Response	3.72	0.66
Public Health Communication Effectiveness (Overall)	3.73	0.63

Table 2 shows the descriptive statistics like mean scores and standard deviations of the major study variables. The mean value for media literacy (M = 3.84) indicates a moderately high level of media literacy among participants of the study. Similarly, the mean scores (M = 3.79) for message comprehension indicate that members have high level of understanding the message, trust in health

information (M = 3.68) represents the moderate level of understanding, and behavioral response (M = 3.72) suggest generally positive perceptions of public health communication. On the flip side only few members displayed relatively low standard deviations that indicate consistency in response.

Scale	Number of Items	Cronbach's Alpha
Media Literacy	15	0.86
Public Health Communication Effectiveness	12	0.88
Behavioral Response	8	0.82

Note: Cronbach's Alpha values above 0.70 indicate acceptable internal consistency.

Table 3 presents the Cronbach alpha results that was applied by the researcher to test the validity and reliability of the data collection tools. The Cronbach's Alpha values for media literacy ($\alpha = 0.86$), public health communication effectiveness

($\alpha = 0.88$), and behavioral response ($\alpha = 0.82$) exceed the recommended threshold of 0.70. The results presented above confirm strong internal consistency and reliability of the questionnaire and the scales used in the study, indicating that the questionnaire items effectively measured the intended constructs.

Variable	Media Literacy	PHC Effectiveness
Media Literacy	1	.62**
Public Health Communication Effectiveness	.62**	1

Table 4 demonstrates the data gathered from the questionnaire. Researcher used pearson correlation for analysis of media literacy and its effectiveness towards public health

communication. The outcomes reveal a strong, positive, and statistically significant correlation ($r = .62$, $p < .01$). This finding suggests that the individuals who have high level of media literacy

showed the better trust in health related messages. Moreover, it showed that media literacy increased effectiveness of public health communication because individuals with high media literacy

respond to health-related messages dispersed through digital platforms.

Predictor Variable	B	Std. Error	β	t	Sig.
Constant	1.12	0.21	—	5.33	.000
Media Literacy	0.58	0.04	.61	14.50	.000
Age	0.07	0.03	.09	2.33	.020
Education Level	0.11	0.04	.12	2.75	.006

Multiple regression analysis results were presented in the Table 5. The results of the examining media literacy as a predictor of public health communication effectiveness revealed that media literacy emerged as a significant predictor ($\beta = .61$, $p < .001$), indicating a strong positive influence on communication effectiveness. Age ($\beta = .09$, $p = .020$) and education level ($\beta = .12$, $p = .006$).

Moreover, results also exhibited that significant effects of media literacy was found through the perspective of the participants. These findings suggest that media literacy remains the most influential determinant to promote effective media literacy.

R	R ²	Adjusted R ²	F	Sig.
.65	.42	.41	99.84	.000

Table 6 provides the overall model summary of the regression analysis. Researcher used regression analysis to determine the role of media literacy in promoting health effectiveness. The R² value of 0.42 indicates that 42% of the variance in public health communication. The statistically significant

F-value (F = 99.84, $p < .001$) confirms that the regression model is a good fit for the data and possesses strong explanatory power. Additionally, effectiveness of media literacy lies in health communication with public.

Gender	Mean	SD	t	df	Sig.
Male	3.79	0.63			
Female	3.88	0.59	-1.54	418	.124

Table 7 reports the statistics of the independent samples t-test. Researcher used independent

sample t-test for comparing media literacy scores across gender. Although female respondents

showed a slightly higher mean score ($M = 3.88$) compared to males ($M = 3.79$), the difference was not statistically significant ($p = .124$). This finding

indicates that media literacy is not gender specific rather it is based on the level of media literacy.

Source	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	14.26	2	7.13	19.32	.000
Within Groups	154.10	417	0.37		
Total	168.36	419			

Table 8 presents the results of the one-way ANOVA examining differences in media literacy across education levels. The findings reveal a statistically significant difference among groups ($F = 19.32$, $p < .001$). The data mention in the above table endorses that media literacy varies significantly according to educational attainment. It was also found that participants with higher education levels associated with stronger media literacy skills on the flip side participants with low education showed low level of media literacy. The finding highlighted that the role of education in enhancing individuals' ability to critically evaluate digital health information.

5.2 Results and Discussion

This study examined media literacy as a determinant of effective public health communication in the digital age, focusing on the general public of Bahawalpur. The findings of the study proved to be significant that media literacy plays constructive role how individuals respond to public health messages that were presented to them through digital media platforms.

The data related to media literacy and understanding of public health messages revealed that a moderately high level of media literacy among respondents was positively associated with message comprehension. When a health related message was presented to them they easily understand the message. The strong and

statistically significant correlation between media literacy and public health communication effectiveness confirms that individuals with higher media literacy are better able to understand health-related information. Therefore, the finding of the present study supports the first research question and aligns with cognitive processing theories, which suggest that individuals equipped with critical media skills engage in deeper evaluation and interpretation of digital content.

Participants shared their point of view about media literacy and behavioral response, data gathered from the questionnaire revealed that media literacy is productive for promoting the positive behavior in the public. Researcher applied regression analysis and the results confirmed that media literacy is the strongest predictor of positive behavioral responses to public health communication. Moreover, it was also found that individuals prefer to adopt preventive behavior. Respondents with higher media literacy were more willing to follow health guidelines and engage in preventive health behaviors. This finding directly addresses the second research question and highlights the practical importance of media literacy in promoting public compliance with public health initiatives.

Results related to the influence of demographic factors revealed that age and education level showed statistically significant effects. One cannot deny the impact of age and education on their

influence to media literacy. Gender differences in media literacy were not statistically significant, indicating that media literacy skills are not inherently gender-based within the study population. However, the ANOVA results revealed that education significantly influences media literacy levels, suggesting that educational attainment enhances individuals' critical engagement with digital health information. These findings respond to the third research question by demonstrating that demographic factors moderate but do not override the role of media literacy. Overall, the regression model explained 42% of the variance in public health communication effectiveness, indicating substantial explanatory power. This underscores media literacy as a central determinant in the digital health communication process.

RQ1: How does media literacy influence understanding and acceptance of public health messages online?

The findings indicate that media literacy significantly enhances individuals' ability to comprehend and critically evaluate public health messages. The data gathered from the questionnaire revealed that higher media literacy leads to better interpretation, reduced confusion, and increased acceptance of credible health information. Similarly, audience shared their point of view that acceptance of public health messages often leads to positive health behaviors and save them in the pandemics. They adhere to preventive measures, healthy lifestyle choices, and compliance with health advisories after they attended health related messages through media. Media literacy strengthens the link between understanding and action by enabling informed decision-making.

RQ2: What is the relationship between media literacy and adherence to public health guidance?

A strong positive relationship was found between media literacy and adherence to public health guidelines. The findings of the study revealed that media-literate individuals demonstrated greater willingness to follow health recommendations and engage in preventive behaviors. Participants of the study claimed that after having higher media literacy, they are more adhere to public health guidance such as vaccination, mask-wearing, hygiene practices, and health screenings.

RQ3: How do demographic factors moderate the relationship between media literacy and public health communication effectiveness?

Education and age moderate this relationship to some extent, with higher education associated with greater media literacy. However, media literacy remains the most influential factor, while gender does not significantly affect media literacy levels. The findings of the study revealed that media literacy is most effective when public health communication was design according to the demographics of the audience's age, education, socioeconomic status, gender, geography and culture.

Conclusion

This study concludes that media literacy is an important factor of effective public health communication in this digital age. Public is confused because information is overload and widespread misinformation. It challenges their ability to critically evaluate digital media content. The findings of this study demonstrated that media literacy exerts a stronger influence on public health communication effectiveness than demographic variables such as age and gender. By empirically establishing the role of media literacy, this study contributes to both communication theory and public health practice. It highlights the

necessity of moving beyond information dissemination strategies toward capacity-building approaches that enhance critical media engagement among the public. According to the findings of the study this study can be implicated for tailoring public health campaigns for the demographic variables. This study can be supportive for the policy makers that they can address organizational inequalities to maximize the benefits of media literacy.

Recommendations for Future Research

- This study can be helpful for the future studies as they should employ longitudinal designs to examine changes in media literacy and health behavior over time.
- Comparative studies across different regions of Pakistan can provide broader generalizability as this study just focused the south Punjab region.
- In the light of findings, qualitative research may further explore cognitive and emotional processes underlying media literacy and health communication.

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